

#	Query	Limiters/Expanders	Last Run Via	Results
S80	S78 AND S79	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	130
S79		Limiters - Published Date: 20220101-20231231; Language: Danish, English, Norwegian, Swedish Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	599,214
S78	S21 AND S68 AND S77	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	1,294
S77	(S22 OR S23 OR S24 OR S25 OR S26 OR S27 OR S28 OR S29 OR S30 OR S31 OR S32 OR S33 OR S34 OR S35 OR S36 OR S37 OR S38 OR S39 OR S40 OR S41 OR S42 OR S43 OR S44 OR S45 OR S46 OR S47 OR S48 OR S49 OR S50 OR S51 OR S52 OR S53 OR S54 OR S55 OR S56 OR S57 OR S58 OR S59 OR S76)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	1,466,952
S76	S74 N5 S75	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	4,590
S75	S72 OR S73	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	437,139
S74	S69 OR S70 OR S71	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	23,201
S73	communicat*	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	240,530
S72	(MH "Communication+")	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	318,213
S71	e-health	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	21,359
S70	ehealth	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	21,908
S69	(electronic N3 health N3 service*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	195
S68	S60 OR S61 OR S62 OR S63 OR S64 OR S65 OR S66 OR S67	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	175,734
S67	(postoperativ* N3 rehabilitation*) OR (post-operativ* N3 rehabilitation*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	2,293
S66	(MH "Length of Stay") OR (Length* N3 stay*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search	71,091

			Database - CINAHL	
S65	(transition* N3 home*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	1,994
S64	(post N3 discharg*) OR post-discharg*	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	5,594
S63	(MH "Patient Discharge+") OR "discharg**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	110,480
S62	(hospital* N3 home*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	9,849
S61	(return* N3 home*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	2,204
S60	(short N3 time N3 stay*) OR (short N3 term N3 stay*) OR (short N3 time N3 hospitalization*) OR (short N3 term N3 hospitalization*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	415
S59	(MH "Adaptation, Physiological+") OR (MH "Adaptation, Psychological+") OR (emotional N3 adjust*) OR (adapt* N3 behav*) OR (psychologic* N3 adjust*) OR (adapt* N3 psychologic*) OR (physiologic* N3 adjust*) OR (physiologic* N3 adapt*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	53,171
S58	(MH "Prehabilitation") OR "Prehabilitation**" OR (preoperative N3 exercise*) OR (pre-operative exercise*) OR (preoperative N3 educat*) OR (pre-operative N3 educat*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	2,991
S57	(MH "Text Messaging+") OR (text N3 messag*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	6,184
S56	(mobile N3 team\$)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	413
S55	(MH "Rehabilitation+") OR "rehab**" OR "convalescence**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	427,315
S54	(MH "Recovery+") OR "recover**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	143,406
S53	(MH "Home Rehabilitation+") OR (home N3 rehab*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	4,291
S52	(MH "Self-Management") OR (self N3 manag*) OR "self-manag**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	23,489
S51	(MH "Multidisciplinary Care Team+") OR (multidisciplin* N3 car*) OR (multi-disciplin* N3 car*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	55,113
S50	(MH "Health Promotion+") OR (health N3 promot*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	108,879

S49	(MH "Self Care+") OR (self N3 car*) OR (self-car*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	84,297
S48	(MH "Continuity of Patient Care+") OR (patient N3 car*) OR (car* N3 behav*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	402,291
S47	(MH "Patient Education+") OR (patient* N3 educat*) OR (MH "Patient Discharge Education") OR (client* N3 educat*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	105,269
S46	(clinic* N3 teach* N3 method*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	3,562
S45	(MH "Analgesia+") OR "analgesia**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	36,169
S44	(MH "Pain Management") OR (pain N3 manag*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	40,485
S43	(instruction* N3 film*) OR (instruction* N3 video*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	932
S42	(MH "Simulations+") OR "simulation**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	70,080
S41	(active N3 post-discharg* N3 surveillanc*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	3
S40	(remote N3 monitor*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - SmartText Searching	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	3,417
S39	(followup N3 support*) OR (follow-up N3 support*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - SmartText Searching	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	2,244
S38	(followup N3 car*) OR (follow-up N3 car*) OR (continuo* N3 nurs*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - SmartText Searching	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	74
S37	(MH "After Care") OR (after N3 car*) OR "after-car**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	66,235
S36	(real-time N3 support*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	384
S35	(MH "Home Visits") OR (home N3 visit*) OR (house N3 call*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	13,012
S34	(MH "Nursing Informatics") OR (nurs* N3 inform*) OR (health N3 inform* N3 techn*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	20,269
S33	(inform* N3 application*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	2,304
S32	(MH "Medical Informatics") OR (inform* N3 communicat* N3 techn*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	8,172
S31	(health N3 communica*) OR (medic* N3 inform*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search	36,611

			Database - CINAHL	
S30	(MH "Videoconferencing+") OR (video N3 conf*) OR "video-conf**	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	6,684
S29	(MH "Telenursing") OR "telenurs**	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	2,357
S28	(MH "Telerehabilitation") OR (tele N3 rehab*) OR "tele-rehab**	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	757
S27	(MH "Mobile Applications") OR (mobile N3 application*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	13,837
S26	(MH "Tablets") OR "tablet**	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	13,133
S25	(MH "Smartphone") OR "smartphone** OR "smart-phone**	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	12,253
S24	(MH "Telephone+") OR "telephone** OR (MH "Cellular Phone+") OR (cell N3 phone*) OR (mobile N3 phone*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	60,529
S23	(MH "Telehealth+") OR "telehealth** OR "tele-health**	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	36,913
S22	(MH "Telemedicine+") OR "telemedicine**	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	29,978
S21	S6 OR S19 OR S20	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	49,668
S20	(spine* OR spinal* OR lumbar*) N7 (surg* OR neurosurg* OR orthop#ed*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	30,185
S19	S12 AND S18	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	35,689
S18	S13 OR S14 OR S15 OR S16 OR S17	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	127,766
S17	(MH "Lumbar Vertebrae") OR (lumbar N3 vertebra*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	21,335
S16	(MH "Spine+") OR "spine" OR (spin* N3 column*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	74,263
S15	(MH "Spinal Diseases+") OR (spinal N3 disease*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	42,386
S14	(MH "Radiculopathy") OR "radicul**	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	5,600
S13	(MH "Low Back Pain") OR (low N3 back N3 pain) OR (back N3 pain)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	44,408
S12	S7 OR S8 OR S9 OR S10 OR S11	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search	214,893

			Database - CINAHL	
S11	(spin* N3 surg*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	23,350
S10	(MH "Orthopedic Surgery+")	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	133,932
S9	(MH "Orthopedics") OR "orthop#edic**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	80,613
S8	(neurosurgical N3 procedure*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	599
S7	(MH "Neurosurgery+") OR "neurosurgery"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	35,772
S6	S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	29,691
S5	(MH "Spinal Diseases+/SU")	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	14,117
S4	(MH "Spinal Fusion") OR (spin* N3 fusion*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	13,182
S3	(MH "Decompression, Surgical+") OR (surg* N3 decompression*)	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	7,610
S2	(MH "Discectomy") OR "discectom**" OR "dissectom**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	4,040
S1	(MH "Laminectomy") OR "laminectomy**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL	3,260